

PLASTICITY MODELING OF THE STRESS-STRAIN BEHAVIOR OF GRANULAR MATERIALS IN THE STRAIN HARDENING AND SOFTENING REGIMES

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ABSTRACT A plasticity model for the stress-strain behavior of granular materials in the strain hardening and strain softening regimes is presented. The model is based on micro-mechanical observations obtained from particulate simulations of the response of granular materials during biaxial loading using the Discrete Element Method (DEM). The DEM modeling was carried out using the Particle Flow Code (PFC), and homogenization techniques were used to convert discrete micro-mechanical quantities to continuum macro-mechanical parameters. In agreement with observations from laboratory testing, DEM modeling showed that deformation of granular materials is initially homogeneous followed by bifurcation causing the formation of one or two narrow shear bands where the deformations are localized. As a result of localized deformation, the load-carrying capacity of the granular assembly reduces with increasing strain and strain softening ensues. Following localization, the DEM modeling focused on the response of the granular material within the shear band, and these observations were then used to establish a continuum model of the post-failure behavior of the granular materials. A non-associated plasticity model was used for the homogeneous strain hardening regime, and the onset of strain localization is predicted using bifurcation theory. Post-localization response was based on the model smeared discontinuity, where it is assumed that elastoplastic deformation comes from the localized deformation of the material in the shear band while the material outside the shear band deforms elastically. Based on the DEM results, the deformation inside the shear band was modeled following simple shear condition. This localized deformation is then averaged over a sampling volume of the material. The thickness, orientation, and degree of principal stress rotation and non-coaxiality within the shear band, which are all needed to establish the simple shear stress-strain behavior of the shear band, were also all obtained from DEM results. The complete continuum plasticity model was shown to be capable of replicating the DEM results on the full spectrum of the stress-strain behavior of granular materials from strain hardening to failure and strain softening. Use of the model in simulating the response of RF-Hostun sand under bi-axial plane strain loading showed that the model can realistically reproduce real granular material behavior. One of the main findings from both micro and macro-mechanical modeling is the importance of shear band thickness in relation to the sampling volume in determining the magnitude of strain softening.